

Gender, Cultural Capital and the Politics of Legitimacy in Sattriya Dance of Assam, India

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Abstract

This article examines the gendered organisation of authority in Sattriya, the Vaishnavite classical dance tradition of Assam, through Pierre Bourdieu's concepts of cultural capital, field and habitus. Historically confined to male monastic institutions (sattras), Sattriya functioned as a closed system of religious and cultural transmission in which only celibate male disciples were authorised to acquire, perform and transmit legitimate knowledge. Drawing on ethnographic interviews and participant observation at Uttar Kamalabari Satra, Majuli, Assam in India, the paper demonstrates how control over embodied technique, pedagogical authority and ritual performance constituted a monopoly over legitimate cultural competence. The gradual entry of women into Sattriya since the mid-twentieth century has reconfigured this field by redistributing access to embodied, institutional and symbolic capital. However, women's participation continues to be negotiated through moral regulation, menstrual taboos, and persistent claims to monastic authenticity. The article argues that contemporary debates over performance, choreography and pedagogy are not merely aesthetic disagreements but struggles over symbolic authority and the right to define legitimate Sattriya itself.

Keywords

Sattriya, Gender, Cultural Capital, Satra.

Introduction

Sattriya is a Vaishnavite dance-drama tradition of Assam that originated within the satra monasteries established during the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries under the neo-Vaishnavite movement led by Srimanta Sankardeva and his disciples. Emerging from the devotional theatrical form of Ankiya Naat, Sattriya integrated elements of classical Sanskrit dramaturgy with local narrative and performative practices such as Ojapali, Putola Nach and Khuliya Bhaona. Although diverse folk dance and ritual traditions—many of them performed by women—were widespread in pre-Vaishnavite Assam, Sattriya developed as a monastic, ritualised and highly regulated form of performance.

The consolidation of Vaishnavite institutions gradually transformed performance into a disciplined devotional practice. Dance, music and theatre became instruments of religious pedagogy and moral cultivation rather than public entertainment. Females have been an important part of the folk dances of Assam from the very beginning. "In *Kherai*, the most important *puja* of the Bodos, in which they worship their principal god Bathou or Siva, a girl must perform the religious dance in front of the altar. A Deodhani girl in a trance like inspired state, goes on dancing to the accompaniment of *kham* (drum) and *ciphung* (flute) propitiating many deity beginning with Siva and ending with Lakshmi; she at one stage takes a sword and a shield and performs a virile war-dance" (Das 1972 : 126). While women occupied important ritual and performative roles in several Assamese folk traditions—such as Deodhani and Kherai dances—Sattriya evolved within a monastic environment that restricted access to training, performance and transmission almost exclusively to male disciples.

Objective of study

This article situates Sattriya within the broader historical transformation of performance cultures in India, in which several temple-based dance traditions declined following colonial intervention, legal reforms and changing moral regimes.

Review of Literature

It is evident that before the era of Sankardeva, dance was prevalent in Assam, as it was in other parts of India. Similar to the temple dances or *Devadasi Nritya* traditions that existed across the country, Assam also had a comparable form known as *Devanati* or *Nati* dance (Barua & Pegu:2025).

The term *Devadasi*, meaning "God's maid" or "maiden servant," denotes a woman artist ritually married to a deity, practicing a form of sacred theogamy. The *Devadasis* played a crucial role in Indian temples—they cleaned, decorated, lit lamps, chanted hymns, and performed dances in devotion to the deities. In addition, they trained many young girls in classical music and dance, thereby keeping these classical art forms alive.

However, with changing times and the emergence of strong legislative systems, these temple dancers gradually lost their dignity and social standing. The temple priests and other members of the higher class, including those associated with royal courts, began to treat them as commodities, exploiting them physically and socially. The decline in patronage and loss of respect forced many temple dancers to abandon their art, leading to the eventual disappearance and distortion of this once-sacred tradition from Indian temples. "There was a class of people who underwent intensive training in temple dances. Girls known as *natis* were thus trained for the temples at Dubi, Hajo, Biswanath and Dergaon. There was a caste of people in Assam known as *Naat Kalita*. But these people have long discontinued their art due to social negligence and apathy" (Das 1972 : 128).

Analysis

Bharatanatyam and Odissi later emerged from the *Devadasi* tradition and flourished as new classical performing arts of India. In Assam too, the *Devanati* dance tradition eventually faded away.

This kind of ritualistic dancing tradition was not confined to India alone; similar practices existed in different parts of the world. It may be observed that most ancient cultures in Europe, the Middle East, West Africa, and South Asia practiced the ritual of dedicating young girls to temples, where they were often subjected to sexual exploitation by the priests or devotees of the deity.

"These kinds of ceremonial slavery or sexual servitude, such as *Trokosi* in some parts of West Africa and *Devadâsis* in India, appear to have continued till today, defying legislation. Similar to the *Devadâsis* system, *Trokosi* is an ancient custom from West Africa in which young girls, especially virgins, are sent to a shrine as atonement for the transgression of a family member. Many West African states, including Ghana, Togo, Benin, and parts of Nigeria, practice *Trokosi*. Despite the Ghanaian government's 1998 ban on forced labour and slavery, the 'slave of the gods' religion continues to exist, with numerous women and girls being held as sex slaves. Human rights activists have expressed concern that the government has not effectively eliminated the practice of *Trokosi*, which has proven challenging to eradicate despite official legislation." (Barua & Pegu 2025:19). Unlike many temple traditions that were later reconstructed as modern classical dance forms, Sattriya remained continuously practiced inside the *satra* system. This continuity endowed it with exceptional symbolic authority, but also produced a tightly guarded structure of legitimacy.

The central question guiding this study is: how is legitimacy in Sattriya produced, protected and challenged? Drawing on Bourdieu's theory, the article argues that the struggle over who is authorised to perform, teach and represent Sattriya constitutes a struggle over cultural capital and symbolic power rather than a mere dispute over artistic style.

Sattriya as a Monastic field of Cultural Production

The *satra* functions not only as a devotional institution but as a specialised field of cultural production. Within this field, access to knowledge of dance, music, scripture and dramaturgy is regulated through residential monastic life, strict moral discipline and long-term apprenticeship.

Historically, the pedagogical system of the *satras* relied on oral transmission (Cantlie:1984). Disciples learned dance technique, rhythmic syllables, musical repertoires and performance conventions through prolonged bodily practice under senior teachers. This process cultivated not only technical competence but also a devotional orientation, emotional discipline and hierarchical deference.

Performance within the *satra* is primarily ritual. Daily devotional singing and rhythmic accompaniment using *khol* (drum) and *taal* (cymbals) continue irrespective of an audience. On special occasions such as *tithis* (anniversaries), full dance sequences are performed as offerings rather than spectacles. The absence of an audience-oriented logic further distinguishes monastic Sattriya from stage-based classical dance.

The field thus defines its own internal rules of value: legitimacy derives from long-term monastic residence, spiritual discipline and genealogical transmission rather than from public recognition, professional success or institutional certification outside the *satra*.

Cultural Capital and Male Monopolization

Following Bourdieu, cultural capital exists in embodied, objectified and institutionalised states (1986). In Sattriya, embodied capital is acquired through highly codified bodily dispositions: postures, footwork, eye movements, rhythmic sensitivity and controlled emotional expression. Objectified capital consists of musical compositions, choreographic

structures, performance repertoires and ritual texts. Institutionalised capital appears in the authority of recognised borbayans and borgayans and, more recently, in state cultural institutions and awards.

Historically, access to all three forms of capital was mediated almost entirely by male religious authority. Although women were not excluded from religious congregations in the Vaishnavite tradition more broadly, they were excluded from the monastic training structures through which legitimate Sattriya knowledge circulated.

Within the satra, male disciples became the exclusive custodians and authorised transmitters of this capital. Recognition inside the field depended not on individual ability alone but on institutional validation. Consequently, even if women possessed comparable technical competence, they lacked the symbolic conditions required for their competence to be recognised as legitimate.

This monopolisation produced what Bourdieu terms a monopoly of legitimate competence. Male monastic bodies became the normative carriers of tradition, while alternative embodiments were rendered inauthentic or secondary.

Gendered Embodiment and the Production of Habitus

Habitus refers to durable, embodied dispositions shaped by long-term socialisation (Grenfell 2008). In Sattriya, habitus is actively produced through monastic living, devotional discipline, hierarchical pedagogies and codified bodily training.

A distinctive feature of this tradition is that male performers enact both masculine and feminine dance styles. When performing female-styled dances such as Sali Nritya, male disciples adopt refined gestures, soft torso movements, controlled glances and delicately stylised abhinaya. Costumes are designed to suggest femininity without accommodating actual female bodies.

Ethnographic observation at Uttar Kamalabari Satra shows that only the most accomplished disciples are entrusted with performing female-styled dances during ritual occasions. The same performers often present vigorous male dances such as Bahar before transforming into the restrained and graceful bodily idiom of Sali Nritya.

This arrangement produces a paradoxical gendered habitus: femininity is institutionalised as a male-performed and male-regulated aesthetic category. Female bodily experience is excluded from the production of feminine representation itself. As a result, women's habitus is historically prevented from accumulating cultural capital inside the field.

Women who enter Sattriya today therefore do not simply acquire technique; they confront a field whose embodied norms were structured without reference to women's social and corporeal realities.

Historical Exclusion and Moral Regulation

The exclusion of women from monastic Sattriya was reinforced by both institutional rules and moral rationales. Satra life is structured around celibacy and controlled social interaction. Women's presence during festivals and performances was traditionally restricted on the grounds that it could disrupt monastic discipline.

Contemporary interviews indicate that these logics continue to operate in modified forms. At Uttar Kamalabari Satra, women are discouraged from entering during menstruation, and senior disciples including Bargayans and Barbayans often express concern that marriage and domestic responsibilities limit women's capacity to sustain long-term training. With the formation of the Satra institutions—male-centered religious monasteries where only male disciples live under strict spiritual discipline—the responsibility of maintaining, performing, and transmitting Sattriya culture fell almost entirely to men. Women were traditionally kept out of Satra rituals and festivals because their presence was believed to distract young celibate disciples. In an open-ended interview, Upen Bargayan (46), a disciple from Uttar Kamalabari Satra, explained that women are still not permitted to enter a Satra during menstruation. Such narratives simultaneously naturalise gendered divisions of labour and justify historical patterns of exclusion.

Importantly, this exclusion does not originate from doctrinal hostility towards women within Vaishnavism. Historical accounts indicate women's participation in devotional and intellectual life and even their recognition as religious leaders in certain sub-sects. Rather, exclusion emerges from the institutional architecture of monastic training through which cultural capital circulates.

Women's Entry and the Reconfiguration of the field

The entry of women into Sattriya began in the mid-twentieth century, following broader processes of secularisation, public performance and cultural institutionalisation. This movement was pioneered by Rashewar Saikia Borbayan, who initiated female participation in the 1960s. Sarma noted that "The inclusion of women in our traditionally male-centered Sattriya dance can be regarded as the beginning of a 'Women's Performing Revolution' in Sattriya (2022:89)". The pioneering role of Rashewar Saikia Borbayan in training women from the 1950s onwards marked a decisive rupture with monastic exclusivity.

Women gradually acquired embodied cultural capital through rigorous training under male gurus and gained institutional capital through public performances, cultural organisations and later state recognition. Their increasing visibility expanded Sattriya beyond ritual devotion into a professionalised and pedagogical field.

Women performers also contributed to the growth of choreographed Sattriya presentations, particularly abhinaya-oriented works based on borgeet and Ankiya Naat episodes. These choreographies enhanced accessibility and audience appeal, facilitating the circulation of Sattriya on national and international stages.

However, this expansion introduced new tensions. Monastic practitioners express concern that choreographed adaptations, abbreviated pure dance segments and performances set to non-Sattriya musical genres blur the boundary between classical form and stylistic borrowing. Such anxieties reflect deeper struggles over who possesses the authority to define Sattriya.

The growing numerical dominance of women learners outside the satras intensifies this symbolic struggle. While women now hold positions in academic institutions, cultural policy forums and national award systems, their legitimacy within the monastic field remains partial and conditional.

Ongoing Tensions and the Politics of Legitimacy

Several satras continue to deny women access to ritual performance and institutional recognition as legitimate bearers of the tradition. Women dancers must therefore operate across overlapping but unequal fields: the monastic field that controls authenticity and the public cultural field that confers visibility, professional status and economic sustainability.

Cultural capital in Sattriya is thus continuously negotiated. Women must repeatedly demonstrate discipline, devotion and technical mastery to counter assumptions that associate innovation and choreography with dilution. At the same time, male monastic actors defend their authority by invoking genealogical continuity, ritual purity and the limits of short-term training outside residential monastic life.

The field is therefore characterised by a dual legitimacy structure: monastic authenticity and public institutional recognition coexist, but remain hierarchically ordered.

Conclusion

Sattriya offers a revealing case of how gender, cultural capital and symbolic authority intersect in a living classical tradition. Through Bourdieu's analytical framework, it becomes evident that struggles over who may perform, teach and represent Sattriya are struggles over legitimate competence and cultural ownership.

Women's entry into Sattriya is not merely an inclusionary process. It actively destabilises the historical monopoly through which male monastic bodies were constituted as the sole legitimate carriers of tradition. Yet, habitus and institutional memory continue to reproduce gendered hierarchies, even when public discourse endorses equality.

Future research may extend this analysis by examining how queer and non-binary performers engage with Sattriya's gendered aesthetics and devotional ethics, and how emerging pedagogical spaces outside the satras reshape the distribution of cultural capital in the long term.

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